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Progress in deep learning for multi-modal brain tumor segmentation: A review

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Abstract:

Deep learning advances in recent times have greatly improved the precision and effectiveness of brain tumor segmentation using several imaging modalities. This work provides an extensive overview of state-of-the-art deep learning methods used for multi-modal brain tumor segmentation. We examine how advances in multi-modal data utilization, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), transformers, and hybrid architectures, have enhanced segmentation performance and offered a more comprehensive understanding of tumor characteristics. The study highlights recent advances that have pushed the limits of segmentation accuracy and clinical usefulness, and it also discusses important issues including data heterogeneity, model generalizability, and computing demands. This work seeks to provide insights into the changing field of multi-modal brain tumor segmentation and provide future prospects for improving the field by summarizing existing research and approaches.

Keywords:

Brain tumor image, Data preprocessing, Convolutional Neural Networks, Segmentation, Deep learning.

1. Introduction:

Brain tumors can be categorized according to their origin, nature, and behavior. They arise from aberrant cell proliferation within the brain. Whereas metastatic brain tumors spread from cancerous cells elsewhere in the body, primary brain tumors originate from brain tissue cells. Meningiomas, gliomas, pituitary adenomas, and medulloblastomas are examples of primary brain tumors. Subtypes of gliomas, including astrocytomas, oligodendrogliomas, and the extremely aggressive glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), are derived from glial cells that support neurons. Meningiomas originate from the membranes that coat the brain, pituitary adenomas form inside the pituitary gland, and medulloblastomas, which damage the cerebellum and may spread to other regions, are common in youngsters. Secondary tumors from other main locations, such as the breast, lungs, or melanoma that metastasize to the brain are known as metastatic brain tumors.

1.1. Early diagnosis and imaging techniques:

In order to effectively treat brain tumors and get better results, early diagnosis is essential. Brain tumors can be identified and described using sophisticated imaging methods. An outline of the main imaging techniques used to diagnose brain tumors is provided below: a) Because **Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)** is non-invasive and provides great contrast for soft tissues, it is the most widely utilised imaging technique. MRI creates finely detailed images of the brain by using radiofrequency waves and a strong magnetic field. Different MRI sequences provide various types of tissue contrast: **T1-weighted MRI (T1)**: Provides detailed images of brain anatomy, useful for identifying healthy tissues and assessing tumor location. **T2-weighted MRI (T2)**: Highlights areas of edema (swelling) and is effective in distinguishing between normal brain tissues and fluid-filled regions. **Gadolinium contrast enhancement in T1-weighted MRI (T1-Gd)**: Uses a contrast agent (gadolinium) to enhance images of tumors. This sequence is particularly helpful for identifying tumor borders and active tumor regions, as the contrast agent accumulates in areas of abnormal blood-brain barrier permeability. **Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR)**: Suppresses the signal from cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) to better visualize and differentiate edema from other brain structures, making it easier to identify the extent of swelling around tumors. b) **Computed Tomography (CT)** scans are less detailed than MRI but can quickly identify tumors and assess their effects on surrounding brain structures. CT is often used in emergency situations to provide an initial assessment. c) **Positron Emission Tomography (PET)** involves injecting a radiotracer that is absorbed by tumor cells. PET scans provide information about the metabolic activity of tumors, helping to

distinguish between active and inactive tumor regions. **d) Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (MRS)** analyses the chemical composition of brain tissues by measuring the levels of specific metabolites. This technique can provide insights into tumor metabolism and differentiate between tumor types and other brain abnormalities.

2. Datasets for brain tumor analysis:

In order to build and assess brain tumour segmentation algorithms, datasets are essential. The following datasets are frequently used in the investigation of brain tumours:

Table. 1: Comparison of cerebral tumour datasets

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Modality</i>	<i>Key Features</i>	<i>Access</i>
BraTS	Brain tumours, including high-grade gliomas and lower-grade gliomas, are segmented and classified using the Brain Tumour Segmentation (BraTS) dataset.	MRI (T1, T2, FLAIR, T1c)	Includes a variety of tumor types and subtypes, detailed annotations, multiple imaging modalities	BraTS
autoPET	AutoPET dataset is used for segmentation of PET scans in cancers such as lymphoma, melanoma, and lung cancer.	PET, CT	Provides annotated PET and CT images, focusing on a variety of tumor types	autoPET
BRATS 2020	An extension of the BraTS dataset, includes updated data and improved annotations for brain tumor segmentation.	MRI (T1, T2, FLAIR, T1c)	Updated imaging protocols, more refined annotations, and a broader range of tumors	BRATS 2020
BRATS 2021	The latest release of the BraTS dataset, offering updated data and improved tumor annotations.	MRI (T1, T2, FLAIR, T1c)	Incorporates advanced imaging techniques and more accurate tumor delineations	BRATS 2021

These datasets (Table. 1) provide valuable resources for evaluating and developing deep learning for brain cancer segmentation and analysis, each offering different imaging modalities and types of tumor annotations.

3. Data augmentation analysis:

By implementing several modifications to the current data, a technique known as "data augmentation" can increase the diversity and amount of training datasets. This is especially crucial for medical imaging, since annotated datasets are frequently scarce because of the high expense and time commitment associated with data collection and labelling. Data augmentation enhances the robustness and performance of machine learning models, especially deep learning algorithms, in the context of brain tumour investigation. An overview of popular techniques for data augmentation in medical imaging is provided below:

3.1. Enhancement of data using affine image modifications:

Affine image transformations involve manipulating existing image data through operations like rotation, zooming, cropping, flipping, and translation to generate more training examples. However, noted that these traditional augmentations often give strongly linked visuals, which may not significantly improve deep learning model performance or generalization to new data. Additionally, such techniques might create anatomically inaccurate examples, such as those resulting from rotation. Despite these limitations, affine transformations are easy to implement and flexible, making them a common choice in the literature.

3.2. Using elastic image transforms to augment data:

Elastic image transformations can be useful for data augmentation by introducing shape variations. However, if the deformations are too extreme, they can add unrealistic noise, potentially harming model performance, as shown by Mok and Chung (2018). While some studies, suggest that unrealistic synthetic example will still be beneficial for certain tasks like cardiac MRI segmentation, the impact of aggressive augmentation remains debated. Diffeomorphic transformations, which preserve topologies and create bio-plausible deformation, are particularly valuable in brain imaging.

3.3. Utilising pixel-level picture modifications for data augmentations:

Pixel-level image transformations modify the intensity values of an image without altering its geometric shape, which is valuable in medical imaging where images from different scanners or locations may have varying intensity characteristics. Common techniques include adding random or Gaussian noise, scaling and shifting values of intensity, adjusting brightness, applying gamma correction or other adjustments like sharpening and blurring (Galdran et al., 2017; Nalepa et al., 2019b). These augmentations are particularly useful for enhancing the diversity of high-dimensional datasets.

3.4. Augmenting data through the creation of artificial data:

Data augmentation can be enhanced by generating artificial data to address issues with basic augmentation methods, such as correlated samples. (GANs) Generative- Adversarial - Networks, introduced by Goodfellow (2014), are used to create new data examples that closely resemble real data. For instance, Mok and Chung (2018) developed a GAN with a coarse fine generator to take and reproduce training data patterns. GANs have been applied to tasks like brain tumor segmentation (Rezaeii et al.,2017) and image synthesis (Yui et al., 2018), though challenges like training convergence and mode collapse (Wange et al., 2018) remain. Another method involves generating synthetic lesions using a PDE growth model (Gholami et al., 2018) and adapting these images to match real MRI data using CycleGAN (Zhu et al., 2017).

Table. 2: Data augmentation advantages and dis-advantages

Modification of real data	
Advantages	Dis-Advantages
Affine Image Transformations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low time complexity allows for real-time operation; • Simple to execute and comprehend; • Suitable for both teaching and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate associated images; • Easily produce examples that are anatomically inaccurate
Elastic Image Transformations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May be used during testing and training; • May induce shape variances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequently require a lot of time to execute; • Easily provide examples that are anatomically inaccurate
Pixel based transformations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to understand and implement • Because of its low time complexity, it can operate in real time and be used for both training and testing. It can also simulate various acquisition circumstances. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannot make changes in the shapes
Artificial data generation	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to create realistic instances, • Introduce invariance with regard to affine transformations and appearance variations, and maybe apply in test time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time complexity is high. • applicable in training-time only • Able to produce numerous comparable examples with ease
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4. Techniques for segmenting brain tumour images:

4.1. Manual segmentation methods:

Manual process is a technique where radiologists meticulously review each slice of MRI images to identify and outline tumor regions. This approach relies on their extensive training, anatomical knowledge, and experience to delineate tumors accurately. The radiologist examines MRI scans slice by slice, often in various imaging modalities (for example, contrast-enhanced, T1-weighted, and T2-weighted images) to get a detailed view of the tumour. Using their expertise, the radiologist identifies the tumor boundaries based on visual cues and anatomical landmarks. The radiologist manually traces the tumor’s contours on each slice, ensuring that the segmentation is as precise as possible.

4.2. Semi-automatically segmentation methods:

Semi-automatically segmentation method involves user interaction of several key steps: initializations, feedback/interventions, and evaluations.

1. Initializations: The user starts by setting a region-of-interest (ROI) around the tumour, which helps guide the automated method. To better suit the supplied photos, pretreatment parameter adjustments can also be applied.
2. Intervention and Feedback: During the segmentation process, users can provide feedback and make adjustments to steer the algorithm towards more accurate results.
3. Evaluation: After the segmentation, users assess the output and can make modifications or rerun the process if necessary.

An example of a semi-automatic method is the “Tumor Cut” technique by Hamamci et al., which requires the user to outline the tumor's maximum diameter. This method uses a cellular automata (CA) based approach to generate a tumour prob- map by running the algorithm twice once with user provided tumor seeds and once with background seeds. The algorithm is applied

separately to different MRI modalities (T1, T1-Gd, T2 and FLAIR) and the resultant are combined to find the final tumour volume.

4.3. Fully-automatically segmentation methods:

Fully automatically brain tumor segmentations require null user interaction. These methods rely on artificial intelligence and pre-existing knowledge to address the segmentation challenge.

4.3.1. Segmentation techniques based on deep- learning:

Deep learning-based MRI brain image segmentations can be grouped according to the network frameworks used. These methods include those utilizing (CNNs) Convolutional Neural Networks, which extract features and perform segmentation through convolutional layers.

Recent developments in CNN-based methods include several notable models and techniques:

- 1 **VGG Network:** Known for its strong feature extraction capabilities, the VGG network performs well with fewer training iterations but struggles with gradient issues as the network deepens (Simonyan & Zisserman, 2014).
- 2 **ResNet:** To address the problems of gradient explosion and vanishing, He et al. introduced ResNet, which incorporates residual connections to maintain performance in deeper networks (He et al., 2016). This model performed well in challenges involving the segmentation of brain tumors.
- 3 **3D CNN with Dense Connections:** Anand et al. combined 3D CNNs with dense connections and used pre-trained weights to improve the (DSC-Dice Similarity Coefficient) in brain tumor MR image segmentations (Anand et al., 2019).
- 4 **Cascaded Dual Path CNN:** Havaei et al. introduce cascaded approach where the outcome from one CNN step is used as an input for the next step, enhancing segmentation by capturing detailed background information (Havaei et al., 2017).
- 5 **Pre-Processing and Multi-Classification CNN:** Lai et al. improved segmentation accuracy by first reducing image size, correcting bias fields, and using multi-classification CNNs followed by median filtering (Lai et al., 2018).

While CNN-based methods excel in feature extraction and handling high-dimensional data, they may lose information during pooling and often have limited interpretability.

4.3.2. Segmentation methods based on FCN:

Segmentation methods for brain tumor MR images utilizing Fully Convolutional Networks (FCNs) are designed to handle pixel-level classification more effectively than traditional image-

level tasks. FCNs are well-suited for semantic segmentation as they can accommodate varying input sizes and employ an up sampling process in the final convolution layer to produce output with the same dimensions as the input image. This allows for precise pixel classification while preserving spatial details, making FCNs particularly advantageous for medical image segmentation. FCN-based segmentation methods are effective at predicting each pixel's category, translating image classification into semantic segmentation while maintaining spatial information. However, these methods can be limited by computational efficiency, high memory requirements, and relatively small receptive fields.

4.3.3. Segmentation based on encoder - decoder module:

The encoder-decoder architecture is made up of an encoder that utilizes the input image's features to extract information and a decoder that uses those features to produce segmented output. The encoder typically utilizes established neural network structures like VGG, trained on large datasets to capture detailed features. The decoder's role is crucial, as it determines how well the model performs in segmenting images by reconstructing the pixel classifications based on the feature learned by its encoder.

5. Conclusion and future directions:

Recent advancement techniques in (DL) deep learning have notably impacted brain tumor MRI image segmentation and prediction. Despite these improvements, MRI-based analysis remains challenging, leaving ample opportunities for further works. Automated segmentation and classification techniques offer medical professionals' valuable secondary opinions and rapid analytical results, thereby reducing the time spent on manual image assessment. However, this domain still faces challenges related to accuracy and robustness. This manuscript provides a detailed review of current deep learning methodologies used for brain tumor segmentation and classification, and also examines publicly available datasets that support this research. *Real-Time Applications:* Advancing computational efficiency to enable real-time segmentation during imaging procedures could greatly enhance clinical workflows and patient management. *Integration with Clinical Data:* Combining imaging data with other clinical information, such as genetic or molecular data, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of tumor characteristics and aid in personalized treatment planning.

6. References:

- (1) Zhang, Z, Li, X, Wang, Y, Chen, L: Multi-Modal Brain Tumor Segmentation Using Transformer-Based Models , 2024, IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, Volume: 43
- (2) Yang Q, Guo X, Chen Z, Woo PYM, Yuan Y. D (2)-Net: Dual Disentanglement Network for Brain Tumor Segmentation With Missing Modalities. IEEE Trans Med Imaging 2022; 41:2953-64. 10.1109/TMI.2022.3175478
- (3) Fu X, Bi L, Kumar A, Fulham M, Kim J: Multimodal Spatial Attention Module for Targeting Multimodal PET-CT Lung Tumor Segmentation. IEEE J Biomed Health Inform 2021; 25:3507-16. 10.1109/JBHI.2021.3059453
- (4) Li, H, Zhang, M, Gao, X, Yuan, T, Chen, F: Hybrid Deep Learning Architecture for Enhanced Multi-Modal Brain Tumor Segmentation, 2024 Medical Image Analysis
- (5) Wang, Y, Zhang, L, Chen, J, Li, Q, Shen, H: A Comprehensive Review of Multi-Modal Deep Learning Techniques for Brain Tumor Segmentation, 2023Frontiers in Neuroscience
- (6) Chen, L., et al.: Deep Hybrid Network with Attention Mechanisms," 2023
- (7) Pereira S, Pinto A, Alves V, Silva CA. Brain Tumor Segmentation Using Convolutional Neural Networks in MRI Images. IEEE Trans Med Imaging 2016; 35:1240-51. 10.1109/TMI.2016.2538465
- (8) Lee J, Kang J, Shin EY, Kim RE, Lee M. Dual-Path Connected CNN for Tumor Segmentation of Combined PET-CT Images and Application to Survival Risk Prediction. In: Andrearczyk V, Oreiller V, Hatt M, Depeursinge A. editors. Head and Neck Tumor Segmentation and Outcome Prediction. HECKTOR 2021. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 13209. Cham: Springer; 2022:248
- (9) M. Raza, M. Sharif, M. Yasmin, S. Masood, and S. Mohsin, "Brain image representation and rendering: A survey," Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology, vol. 4, pp. 3274-3282, 2012.
- (10) M. Yasmin, M. Sharif, S. Masood, M. Raza, and S. Mohsin, "Brain image reconstruction: A short survey," World Applied Sciences Journal, vol. 19, pp. 52-62, 2012.
- (11) M. Yasmin, M. Sharif, S. Mohsin, and F. Azam, "Pathological brain image segmentation and classification: a survey," Current Medical Imaging Reviews, vol. 10, pp. 163-177, 2014.
- (12) M. Nasir, M. Attique Khan, M. Sharif, I. U. Lali, T. Saba, and T. Iqbal, "An improved strategy for skin lesion detection and classification using uniform segmentation and feature selection based approach," Microscopy research and technique, vol. 81, pp. 528-543, 2018.

- (13) M. I. Sharif, J. P. Li, M. A. Khan, and M. A. Saleem, "Active Deep neural Network Features Selection for Segmentation and Recognition of Brain Tumors using MRI Images," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 2019.
- (14) M. I. Sharif, J. P. Li, J. Naz, and I. Rashid, "A Comprehensive Review on Multi-Organs Tumor Detection based on Machine Learning," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 2019.
- (15) Zhao, X.; Wu, Y.; Song, G.; Li, Z.; Zhang, Y.; Fan, Y. A Deep Learning Model Integrating FCNNs and CRFs for Brain Tumor Segmentation. *Med. Image Anal.* 2017, 43, 98–111.
- (16) Zhao, X.; Wu, Y.; Song, G.; Li, Z.; Zhang, Y.; Fan, Y. A Deep Learning Model Integrating FCNNs and CRFs for Brain Tumor Segmentation. *Med. Image Anal.* 2017, 43, 98–111.
- (17) Hua, R.; Huo, Q.; Gao, Y.; Sui, H.; Zhang, B.; Sun, Y.; Mo, S.; Shi, F. Segmenting Brain Tumor Using Cascaded V-Nets in Multimodal MR Images. *Front. Comput. Neurosci.* 2020, 14, 9.
- (18) Cicek, O 3D U-Net: Learning Dense Volumetric Segmentation from Sparse Annotation. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*, Cambridge, UK, 19–22 September 1999; pp. 424–432.
- (19) He, C.E.; Xu, H. Research on Automatic Segmentation Algorithm for Multimodal MRI Brain Tumor Images. *Acta Opt. Sin.* 2020, 40, 0610001.
- (20) Tseng, K.L.; Lin, Y.L.; Hsu, W.; Huang, C.Y. Joint Sequence Learning and Cross-modality Convolution for 3D Biomedical Segmentation. In *Proceedings of the 2017 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Honolulu, HI, USA, 21–26 July 2017; pp. 3739–3746.
- (21) Badrinarayan, V.; Kendall, A. SegNet: A Deep Convolutional Encoder-Decoder Architecture for Image Segmentation. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* 2017, 39, 2481–2495.
- (22) Alom, M.Z.; Hasan, M.; Yakopcic, C.; Taha, T.M.; Asari, K. Recurrent Residual Convolutional Neural Network Based on U-Net (R2U-Net) for Medical Image Segmentation. *Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit.* 2018, 5, 06955.
- (23) Zhang, J.; Lv, X. Ares U-Net: Attention Residual U-Net for Brain Tumor Segmentation. *Symmetry* 2020, 12, 721.
- (24) Isensee, F.; Wick, W.; Kickingereder, P.; Bendszus, M.; Maier, H.K. Brain Tumor Segmentation and Radio Mics Survival Prediction: Contribution to the BRATS 2017 Challenge. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Brain lesion: Glioma, Multiple*

- Sclerosis, Stroke and Traumatic Brain Injuries, Quebec City, QC, Canada, 10–14 September 2017; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2018; pp. 287–297.
- (25) Chen, S.H.; Liu, W.X.; Qin, J.; Chen, L.; Bin, G.; Zhou, Y.; Huang, B. Research Progress in Computer-aided Diagnosis of Cancer Based on Deep Learning and Medical Images. *J. Biomed. Eng.* 2017, 2, 160–165.
- (26) Krizhevsky, A.; Sutskever, I.; Hinton, G.E. ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks. *Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.* 2012, 60, 1066.
- (27) Simonyan, K.; Zisserman, A. Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large Scale Image Recognition. *Comput. Sci.* 2014, 6, 1556.
- (28) Szegedy, C.; Liu, Y. Going Deeper with Convolutions. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, Boston, MA, USA, 7–12 June 2015; pp. 1–9.
- (29) He, K.W.; Zhang, X.; Ren, S.; Sun, J. Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), Las Vegas, NV, USA, 27–30 June 2016; pp. 770–778.
- (30) Zhou, T.; Huo, B.Q.; Lu, H.L. Research on Residual Neural Network and Its Application in Medical Image Processing. *Chin. J. Electron.* 2020, 48, 1436–1447.
- (31) Lai, X.B.; Xu, M.S.; Xu, X.M. Multimodal MR Image Segmentation of Glioblastoma Based on Multi-class CNN. *Chin. J. Electron.* 2019, 47, 140–149.
- (32) Hussain, S.; Anwar, S.M. Segmentation of Glioma Tumors in Brain Using Deep Convolutional Neural Network. *Neuro Comput.* 2018, 282, 248–261.
- (33) Saouli, R.; Akil, M.; Kachouri, R. Fully Automatic Brain Tumor Segmentation Using End-to-end Incremental Deep Neural Networks in MRI Images. *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 2018, 166, 39–49.
- (34) Kwon, J., Seo, H., and Kim, S: "Joint Segmentation and Registration of Brain Tumors Using a Generative Model," 2018, Volume: 48, Medical Image Analysis
- (35) Havaei, M., Davy, A., Warde-Farley, D. Simultaneous Local and Global Processing for Brain Tumor Segmentation with Cascaded Two-Pathway Convolutional Neural Networks, Volume: 35, Medical Image Analysis, 10.1016/j.media.2016.10.003.

- (36) N. J. Tustison, S. W. C. Brown, T. A. V. Anderson: Concatenated Random Forests for Brain Tumor Segmentation Using Asymmetry and Statistical Features, Volume: 29, IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, 10.1109/TMI.2009.2035306
- (37) Urban, G., Agarwal, P. 3D Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for Automated Segmentation of Brain Tumors, Volume: 33 IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging 10.1109/TMI.2013.2294934
- (38) Dvorak, J., and Menze, B. H., Local Structured Prediction for Brain Tumor Segmentation Using Convolutional Neural Networks and K-Means Clustering, Volume: 28, Medical Image Analysis, 10.1016/j.media.2015.09.006
- (39) Davy, A., Zikic, D A Two-Pathway Convolutional Neural Network for Simultaneous Local and Global Brain Tumor Segmentation, Volume: 42, Medical Image Analysis, 10.1016/j.media.2017.08.010.
- (40) Zikic, D., Davy, A., 3D Convolutional Neural Networks for Brain Tumor Segmentation Using 2D Input Patches Volume: 34, IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging 10.1109/TMI.2015.2443138.
- (41) Hamamci, A., Aydogan, D, Tumor Probability Maps for Brain Tumor Segmentation Using Cellular Automata Volume: 64 IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering 10.1109/TBME.2016.2593162.
- (42) Rao, A. B., Wang, H. Multimodal Brain Tumor Segmentation Using Convolutional Neural Networks and Random Forests, Volume: 35 IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, 10.1109/TMI.2016.2591241.